

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter* (IRRN) request that contributors use the following guidelines and style:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N ha: not 60 kg ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotype of BPH in ...
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg ha at 2-week intervals: 7%. 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors: four varieties. But There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the *IRRN* should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source or genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common — not trade — names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in *IRRN* contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Occurrence of rare elements in rice plants

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Mass spectra (Ms-702 mass spectrograph) of the flag leaves of some rice varieties revealed the presence of the rare elements Cr, As, Br, Sr, Ag, Ba, and Pb as well as that of essential elements. We estimated the amount of such rare elements (see table). □

Estimated levels of rare elements in rice plants, Aduthurai, India

Element	Quantity (ppm) of element ^a			
	Ponni	Co 25	IR50	IR26
Cr51	53	52	54	54
As75	2	2	1	2
Br79	3	3	3	3
Sr88	12	14	14	15
Ag107	1	1	1	2
Ba138	1066	1017	1270	1437
Pb208	5	5	5	8

^a The values presented are on ash weight basis relative to silicon, used as an internal standard. Percent silicon is about 18%. The estimate of the volatile element As is approximate because of probable loss during ashing.

CN505-5-32-9, a photoperiod-sensitive semidwarf for rainfed lowlands

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CN505-5-32-9, a promising lowland rice, is from the cross IR26/SML 40-10-4. Selection from F₂ was made at the RRS, Chinsurah, as part of the rainfed lowland

breeding program. Different generations were evaluated for drought tolerance at early vegetative stage, waterlogging (50 cm deepwater), and pest resistance. Considering local yield trials in 1979, 1980, and 1981, in which CN505-5-32-9 averaged 5 t/ha, it was nominated for the 1982 kharif All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project deepwater trials and was evaluated at Tripura (West

Table 1. Yield performance of CN505-5-32-9 at different sites in India.

Site	Yield (t/ha)		Experimental mean (t/ha)	CD (0.05) (kg)	Max water depth ^a (cm)
	CN505-5-32-9	Tilakkachari (check)			
Arundhu tinagar (Tripura)	6.4	4.1	3.9	992	NA
Chinsurah (West Bengal)	5.8	4.3	4.1	654	40
Sindri (Bihar)	3.4	1.3	1.1	826	50
Pulla (Andhra Pradesh)	3.3	1.9	2.3	508	70
Patna (Bihar)	3.1	2.8	2.0	781	NA
Mean	4.4	2.9	2.7		

^a NA = not available.

Table 2. Height and duration of CN505-5-32-9 under different sowing and land situations at RRS Chinsurah (22.9°N, 88.4°E).

Sowing date	Culture	Land situation	Max water depth (cm)	Height (cm)	Days to flower
19 Mar 1982	Transplanted	Lowland	30	112	232
19 Mar	Transplanted	Medium land	5	102	235
30 Mar	Direct seeded	Lowland	40	135	215
31 Mar	Direct seeded	Upland	0	110	225
29 Apr	Transplanted	Lowland	45	113	190
2 Jun	Direct seeded	Lowland	70	138	160